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Abstract book

Braga, 2023

Instituto de Ciências da Terra

Universidade do Minho
Escola de Ciências

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2-3 February 2023

University of Minho | Braga

This work was funded by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) through the project UIDB/04683/2020.

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Secure and sustainable supply of raw materials for EU industry (S34I) project

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Abstract

The SECURE AND SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY OF RAW MATERIALS FOR EU INDUSTRY (S34I) is a Horizon Europe (HORIZON) project that began on the 1st of January, 2023. It involves 19 partners from 12 countries and is coordinated by Ana Teodoro from the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Porto (FCUP). This project will investigate and innovate new data-driven methods to analyse Earth Observation (EO) data, supporting systematic mineral exploration and continuous monitoring of (i) Exploration; (ii) Extraction and; (iii) Closure and post-closure activities to increase European autonomy regarding raw materials (RM) resources, and to use EO data/techniques not only for the management of technical and environmental issues for a green transition but also to support public awareness, mining's social acceptance, and better legislation.

The S34I project will be based on satellite data, airborne, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), ground-based conventional in-situ techniques/methods and fieldwork.

Promising remote sensing methods will be prototyped to contribute to the secure and sustainable supply of RM in Europe while promoting its resilience and independence from non-EU sources.

S34I results will be validated at six different sites as industrial relevant environments and at different phases of the mining life-cycle in order to holistically address the challenges of topic: (i) Land exploration in Spain, to gain knowledge on cobalt (Co) deposits (and associate other critical metals) by effective exploration methods including on old mine waste dumps and tailings; (ii) Shallow waters / coastal exploration at the Iberian Peninsula Atlantic coast, to update the knowledge on coastal metallic placers including critical metals such as Ti, Sn, Li, rare earth elements (REEs) and Au; (iii) Extraction phase in Austria, to address questions associated with construction and chemical materials quarries which are widely spread geographically and; (iv) Closure/post-closure phase in Finland (2 sites) and Germany, to tackle environmental and health impact challenges, critical for modern mining acceptance by the general public, paving the way for independent pollution monitoring tools or early warning of risks.

S34I will exploit Copernicus, Contributing Missions (CCM) and other EU satellite sensors such as PRISMA, TerraSAR-X and COSMO-SkyMED. Different Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques will promote advances and innovative methods that mining stakeholders can use to address the challenges faced in different phases of the mining life-cycle, each represented by at least one study site.

It is anticipated that the project will be finished by July 2025. However, research and distribution will continue even after it is finished to promote communication and knowledge of the creative outcomes.

Keywords: Earth Observation, mining life-cycle, Copernicus, raw materials, land, coastal areas